

Moral Values and Ethics: A Reflection in Children's Literature

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Abstract

Fairy tales and the magical stories of children literature trap the meaning of moral values through the picture books, folk tales and fairy tales, etc. Through these types of tales, children acknowledge struggle between good things and evil things children are able to understand and ponder over the themes reflected from stories. (Children's Literature in India, page 20) Fairy tales help their moral development and make sense of what it is to be human and what are the human values and how can use moral values in society. Fairy tales is important genre of children literature. Themes of fairy tales are unrealistic but they create very positive effect on children's fundamental development.

Generally, these tales explore common themes, such as loyalty, justice, greed, right versus wrong, and the triumph of good over evil. In child development, fairy tales always shape children's leadership qualities. Reading of such literature is not only essential but child should also act according to the stories of fairy tales. It is important for development a child's inner voice and for his/her moral development as well.

In this research paper, the researcher has tried to point out the significance of Fairy Tales through the famous example of Cinderella.

Keywords: Fairy tales, child development, moral values, Cinderella.

Objectives of Research paper

1. To discover Child Psychology
2. To find out moral values.
3. To find out fairy tales and moral values.

Introduction

Psychotherapist Carl Jung tales teach children how to face the basic human struggle, desires, conflicts and relationships in proper way. Perceiving these arts can ultimately impact not only child's health but also on quality of child's personal life or even influence its values and beliefs in the future. The fantasy stories and fairy tales like Beauty and the Beast, Cinderella, Hansel and Gretel, etc. Every story has a moral lesson. When a child listens story, it always gives moral lessons to the child. They can unconsciously learn moral values from them. Because of this role of fairy tales, they are very prominent in the lives of all human beings. A child can learn these moral values, which are stored in his brain /unconscious mind for life time and it recalls them in every situation and apply also accordingly.

Flanner O'Connor, an American writer, has pointed out that for children, storytelling is very useful. She said that "a story is a way to something that can't be said any other way you tell a story because a statement would be inadequate." Children's fantasy stories and the famous fairy tales depict virtues like truthfulness, ethics through different characters present in these stories. They spark as if in a looking glass, and insincerity and cunning are without masks of their boasting to truthfulness and goodness. The great fairy tales and stories make us how we will face the unbelievable truth about ourselves we have to learn from this unvarnished truth that what kind of people we want to be.

Cinderella

Cinderella is very famous and simple story- the story of a kind-hearted and beautiful young girl. Mother of Cinderella died in her childhood. She had step-mother and sisters. They treat Cinderella badly, but she tolerates everything patiently. Cinderella did hard work all day. At the same time her stepsisters and mother sleep in the bed. The poor girl wakes up early in the morning when it was still dark and cold, to start the fire. Cinderella used to all work from morning to night, such as cleaning the house, cooking, ironing clothes etc. A day comes and that day is a lucky day for Cinderella, as Prince of the Town, invites all unmarried girls to a ball in his palace. But the stepmother of Cinderella does not allow her to attend this ball. Her sisters also prohibit her to go palace. She becomes very sad but she cannot do anything. Fortunately, a fairy Godmother arrives there and helps Cinderella a carriage, gown and attractive glass slippers to attend the party. Cinderella reaches the party, she looks very gorgeous. She attracts the attention of everyone including the Prince. Cinderella and Prince dance for long time but at the same time immediately she remembers the words of Fairy godmother, She commanded her not to stay there after midnight, and if she stayed one moment longer the coach would be a pumpkin again, her horses would be mice, and her coachman a rat, and her clothes become just as they were before. As planned by the Fairy, she comes back home before midnight. But by mistake, Cinderella forgets one of her slippers near the palace stairs and Prince decides to search every home of the Kingdom. (CAOS. page no 10) Finally, he finds Cinderella's home; gives her chance to try the shoe, which is the perfect fit. The prince proposes her for marriage; Cinderella accepts instantly. She is not able to express her happiness in words; both of them lived together happily.

What do we learn from this story? The moral lesson child can take from this present fairy tale. "Cinderella" was a very kind Girl. She was not selfish. She was treated very badly by her stepmother and stepsisters but she remains kind and good despite hardship. She always hopes that her sisters and mother will change one day. That is the patience in Cinderella; patience is one thing that can help us achieve whatever we want. She worked hard all day long but never complains about this.

What happened in the End? End was good, a person who works hard is directly helped by God, just like the fairy Godmother comes and helps her. When “Cinderella wants to attend the ball but cannot go there, fairy Godmother appears and provides all things which she needs to attend the ball. Godmother touches her and her clothes turn into cloth-of-gold and silver, all beset with jewels. Cinderella touched her throat, the pearls that encircled her neck. (CAOS page no 10) These lessons should learn from this story that God always helps poor and innocent people such as fairy Godmother help Cinderella.

Cinderella had good qualities like a courage, bravery and perseverance so the moral of present story can be taken ‘if you have courage, patience and kind heard, you will achieve whatever you want and believing in oneself your time also will be come.’ This is magic of time. Kindness is one of the significant lessons that you can learn from this story. “Kindness is always rewarded in the end in one form or other” Cinderella does not leave her lovely and forgiving nature, finally God to confer what she deserved.

Cinderella is a kind soul. She has strength of listening, what is listening? Bad words (abusive words) which are used by her stepmother and sisters of Cinderella. They used to bother her a lot but she remains kind person in every situation. She never loses her lovely nature; result of this kindness is that she becomes the queen of big kingdom. Kindness of Cinderella gave her maturity how to remain grateful and to appreciate others. This lesson helps our kids to perceive the importance of kindness and patience; we should give this lesson to our children. She recognizes herself as a brave girl, very confidently says that, “My stepmother and sisters treated me as like house maid but I want to go the royal ball too” and I deserve it” these words are symbol of self-confidence and strong will-power.

Cinderella gets opportunity of attending that beautiful ball with her family, happiness of her family does not sustain till the end. On the other hand, Cinderella remains there till the last moment. Another important lesson learnt from this story is that immorality and hypocrisy will never bring you success. It always ends badly. In the story of Cinderella, her half-sisters try hard but shoes do not fit, shoes were much too large. Cinderella begged for try the shoes. Her sisters laugh at her with scorn (CAOS. page no 13). The implication is that bad people never get good things.

At the end of the story, Cinderella forgives both of them, showing that forgiveness is a very valuable quality in human being and that Cinderella possesses it. The sisters also hung to her with regret and anguish but at the same time kind hearted Cinderella puts her arms round their necks, further kisses them, and finally forgives them with a big heart for their unkindness (CAOS. page No13). Children should learn forgiveness from Cinderella. In future children have face many difficulties, for that they have to learn forgiveness and would be sustain in society.

By reading the story of Cinderella, Children should learn that a child should be optimistic and that Cinderella was always patient and true to herself, she handled the situation with great patience it turned out to be the best for her similarly, If Children patiently wait out unfavorable conditions, they will emerge victorious in all situations. Child should learn morality and loyalties and it shows that through the Cinderella ability to success through persistence, diligence and positive behavior when faced negative circumstances with negative people.

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